

Celestial Knowledge in Ancient India: Unveiling the Depths of Indigenous Traditional Knowledge

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This study investigates the rich tapestry of Indigenous Traditional Knowledge (ITK) buried in ancient Indian celestial observations. The study focuses on our predecessors' great comprehend of astronomical objects such as stars, planets, and constellations. The research seeks to uncover the subtle linkages between Indigenous knowledge systems and the cosmos via the examination of ancient manuscripts, scriptures, and astronomical treatises.

The process entails a thorough examination of traditional Indian scriptures such as the Vedas, Puranas, and Jyotisha Shastra. Ancient Indian astronomers used complicated mathematical and observational methods, which are given special attention. The study delves further into the cultural and spiritual importance of celestial objects in numerous rites, mythologies, and daily life, demonstrating how indigenous people incorporated astronomical knowledge into their social fabric.

Through this exploration, the study seeks to bridge the gap between traditional knowledge and modern scientific understanding. By recognizing and preserving the Indigenous Traditional Knowledge of celestial objects, we contribute not only to the appreciation of our cultural heritage but also to the broader dialogue on the intersection of ancient wisdom and contemporary scientific inquiry.

The research contributes to the broader understanding of how Indigenous Traditional Knowledge systems are deeply rooted in the observation and interpretation of celestial phenomena. Furthermore, it underscores the relevance of ancient Indian wisdom in the contemporary discourse on astronomy, cultural heritage, and the intersection of science and spirituality.

Keywords: Indigenous Traditional Knowledge (ITK), Astronomical treatises, Celestial observations, AI and ML.